

STRATEGIES AND METHODS FOR DEVELOPING TEACHERS' SKILLS IN THE CONTEXT OF EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND INTERNATIONAL SOLIDARITY

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Abstract

The article delves into the issue of teacher competences in the field of education for sustainable development and international solidarity, through theoretical developments and by presenting the process and partial results of an ongoing research, which is carried out in several investigative directions. The first part of the article is focused on presenting the scientific foundations of the study issue, in the sense of the holistic perspective of education for sustainable development and by emphasizing professional development in the field, with reference to desirable competences (definition, process).

The part dedicated to the investigative approach highlights the variables that favor the improvement of the teacher's professional profile, in the field of education for

sustainable development and international solidarity. The article presents the directions and methodological coordinates of the research, the partial results of an impact study and the premises of a subsequent experimental investigation, focused on the development of the curriculum of a teacher training program.

Keywords: education for sustainable development and international solidarity (ESDIS); comprehensive approach to the competencies associated with education for sustainable development; operationalization of the RIZA model for specification and assessment of competencies; appropriate training strategies for the development of ESDIS-specific competencies.

1. Theoretical framework and premises of research on the issue

Education for Sustainable Development and International Solidarity (ESDIS) has a comprehensive character, in the sense that it brings together values, principles and contents of several educational dimensions. Thus, the epistemological status of ESDIS is focused on the specific contents of education for active citizenship, inclusive education, the development of critical thinking, and intercultural education (Bunăiașu, 2017, p. 25). In this sense, we define education for sustainable development and international solidarity as a hypostasis of postmodern education, which integrates the set of comprehensive concepts and theoretical models, research, educational and didactic methodologies, which aim to develop the cognitive-spiritual profile of the human personality, structured around the areas of general competences, of a transversal nature and which aim, in a correlated and unitary manner, the specified educational areas. Within the framework of the “Acteurs du territoire pour une éducation à la Citoyenneté Mondiale (ACTECIM)” project, where we were part of a team of European experts. Within the project, four areas of competences, desirable for teachers and

students, integrated into the field of education for sustainable development and international solidarity, were defined, operationalized, didactically transposed and tested: 1) civic engagement; 2) affirmation of the critical spirit; 3) awareness of complexity; 4) interculturality (Olivier, coord , 2018). The detailing and specification of competences by structural elements and by performance levels were achieved by applying the RIZA theoretical model, according to which competences are analyzed on three dimensions: analysis and interpretation; actional structures; self-regulation (Trincherro, 2016).

The conceptual premises of our research, regarding the development of teachers' competencies in the field of ESDIS, are complemented by our contributions in the field of intercultural curriculum, approached, in a broad sense, as "a holistic educational project, encompassing all educational processes and intercultural learning experiences , in formal and non-formal contexts and informal within lifelong education ” (Bunăiașu , 2015, p. 45). From the issue of intercultural curriculum, we have selected for valorization, adaptation and development, the following contributions:

- a) the taxonomic system of the general objectives of the intercultural curriculum, ordered in the logic of progression in personality development in the context of cultural diversity and distributed on two axes of objectives: that of intercultural competences and that represented by the values of intercultural awareness (op cit, p. 40-41);
- b) developing the invoked taxonomic system, by introducing elements that target international solidarity, resulting in a picture of intercultural curriculum competencies that can be operationalized in the ESDIS field (Bunăiașu , 2017, pp. 27-29);
- c) curricular structures of a teacher training module in Romania, in the field of education for sustainable development and international solidarity.

The need for an investigative approach following the research in the ACTECIM project targets problematic aspects and anticipatory approaches regarding the development of methodological and curricular tools, which aim to improve teachers' skills, associated with education for sustainable development and international solidarity. To this end, we considered that a teacher training program in the ESDIS field is necessary, with greater curricular consistency and methodological diversity, compared to the training module applied within the project, in Romania. Also, a new impact study will test the fidelity of the project's results over time, at the level of teachers in Dolj County, without generalizing to the partners in Italy and France.

Starting from these premises, we envisioned a complex investigative approach, consisting of two research directions:

- 1) an impact study, regarding the appropriate, efficient and operationalizable methodology of education for sustainable development and international solidarity;
- 2) an experimental research of the teacher training program.

The basic assumption of the research is that a teacher training program, focused on postmodern, diversified training strategies and addressing the four categories of competences in a unified manner, will have a high impact and will greatly favor the professional development of teachers in the field of education for sustainable development and international solidarity. The training strategies and modalities, applied and experimentally validated within the program, will constitute methodological references for the development of teachers' competences, which will facilitate the achievement of the objectives of education for sustainable development and international solidarity.

2. Research aims and objectives

The objectives of the investigative approach are:

1. Testing the subjects' opinions regarding strategies and ways of developing teachers' competences, associated with education for sustainable development and international solidarity;
2. The elaboration and experimental implementation and validation of a teacher training program, focused on the development of the four categories of skills.
3. Systematizing a list of strategies and methods with high impact in the development and affirmation of teachers' competencies in the field of ESDIS.
4. Developing a set of monitoring and evaluation tools in educational practice, for the affirmation of the four categories of competences in the field of education for sustainable development and international solidarity.

3. Research methodology

The subject group was constituted by the mixed sampling technique and consists of 205 subjects, from Dolj and Mehedinți counties. The subject categories in the research sample structure are: a) 120 teachers from pre-university education (primary and preschool teachers, teachers of socio-human subjects, teaching assistants); 60 students in the field of Educational Sciences, bachelor's and master's degrees, from the University of Craiova; 25 experts in the field of education for sustainable development (university teachers, representatives of non-governmental organizations, involved in sustainable development projects).

The research methods and instruments were the following:

- the opinion questionnaire, applied to subjects in first round of research, investigation of opinions regarding education for development sustainable and international solidarity and ways to develop skills specific teachers ;

- focus groups , for detailed analyses regarding each group of subjects;
- experimental method, with the aim multicriterial validation of the teacher training program: theoretical validation of the effects the program in the implementation process, the evaluation on the impact it had on subjects;
- monitoring grids of the training program implementation;
- impact assessment grids of the the training program, by highlighting teachers' professional performances in the educational practice.

4. Results of the impact study

The impact study was organized in March 2022 - September 2023, and the main results were integrated the design of the second phase of the research, dedicated to the pedagogical experiment.

The main instrument of the impact study investigation is the opinion questionnaire, which was pretested and validated , applied to all the subjects and which contain several categories of items . The variables of the impact study, were gradually approached and included in the structure the questionnaire:

- 1) knowledge systems , values and pedagogical concepts of the subjects, in the field of education for sustainable development and international solidarity ;
- 2) educational experiences of the subjects acquired through courses/training sessions or in projects, programs and/or specific ESDIS activities ;
- 3) personal strategies, for self-regulating and self-training , in the field of education for sustainable development.
- 4) modalities to develop teachers' competences , specific to ESDIS;
- 5) methodological suggestions and curricular preferences regarding the teacher training program.

The results from the first three item categories represent independent variables of the impact study, which have influenced subjects' answers from the

next two categories – the dependent variables. These variables have also constituted premises in development of the curricular and research tools, from the experimental investigation phase.

The systematization of the results was carried out by accumulating the responses distributed on the levels "to a large extent", "to a very large extent", from the items with appreciation scales or the values that reflect favorable assessments. In this way, the results with the highest frequency and integrated in the subsequent stages, indicate:

- a) Ways to develop skills teachers, specific to EDDSI :
 - 1) organizing a professional master's programs in the field of education for sustainable development;
 - 2) introducing a mandatory subject or a module of Education for Sustainable Development in bachelor's and master's programs in the socio-human field;
 - 3) continuous teacher training programs, focused on developing specific ESDIS skills;
 - 4) developing teachers' skills in the field of transdisciplinary didactics (Bunăiașu, 2017, p. 31);
 - 5) involving teachers in partnership programs, based on experiential learning in contexts of cultural diversity and affirming international solidarity (op cit, p. 31);
 - 6) developing a unified European-level curricular framework in the field of education for sustainable development.

Table 1.

Subjects' opinions on the forms and methods of developing teachers' competencies, specific to ESDIS

Gro ups	Vari able no.1	Vari able no.2	Vari able no.3	Vari able no.4	Vari able no.5	Vari able no.6
Pre-Universi ty teaching staff	61.6 6%	77.5 0%	84.2 6%	40.8 3%	87.5 0%	50.8 3%
Exp erts	84%	80%	76%	72%	80%	76%
Stud ents	80%	76.6 6%	71.6 6%	71.6 6%	86.6 6%	78.3 3%

b) Methodological opinions and curricular preferences of the subjects, regarding the teacher training program:

- 1) constructivist training strategies, adapted to in-service teacher training programs (Joița, 2006);
- 2) curricular structures focused on training strategies for the development of critical thinking (Albulescu, 2024, Dumitru, 2013);
- 3) innovative methodological tools of e-Didactics, used in virtual learning communities in adult education (Albulescu, Catalano, coord., 2021; Bunăiașu, Vlăduțescu & Strungă, 2014; Bunăiașu, Strungă, 2016);

- 4) methodologies focused on the acquisition and affirmation of interculturalism processes (Gavreliuc, 2011);
- 5) contents that address problems of the contemporary world, which require the application of the principles and strategic directions of education for sustainable development.

Table 2.

Methodological opinions and curricular preferences of the subjects

Groups	Variabl e no.1	Variabl e no.2	Variabl e no.3	Variabl e no.4	Variabl e no.5
Pre- University teachin g staff	51.66 %	75%	73.33 %	54.16 %	83.33 %
Expert s	68%	76%	88%	84%	84%
Studen ts	70%	71.66 %	78.33 %	81.66 %	78.33 %

Conclusions

The theoretical framework of education for sustainable development and international solidarity was systematized and developed based on: the novel elements of the specialized literature, the conceptual and methodological models

from the works analyzed and developed within the ACTECIM project (Trincherro, 2016, Morin, coord, 20218) and our contributions in the field of intercultural curriculum (Bunăiașu, 2015) and of professional identity models in teacher training (Strungă, 2014). The results of the impact study confirm, first of all, the fidelity of the results of the ACTECIM project, at the level of the perceptions and opinions of the subjects in Romania, the Oltenia region. Also, the models and tools regarding the definition, structure, operationalization and evaluation of the four categories of ESDIS specific competencies had a high impact in our research.

The variables presented in the research results will constitute premises for the development of the teacher training program. The statistical analysis confirms the favorable opinions of the subjects regarding the curricular structures and educational strategies of a postmodern approach, in a comprehensive manner, of education for sustainable development and international solidarity. We recorded significant differences at the level of two variables, represented by the European unitary curricular framework in the ESDIS field and the acquisition and affirmation of interculturalism processes. In these criteria, we recorded significant differences between pre-university teachers (who appreciated these variables to a lesser extent) and the other two categories (students and experts); these findings could contribute to the curriculum decision-making process in the development of the training program, regarding awareness and experiential learning, specifically for these thematic subdomains.

Starting from these premises and results of the impact study, we envisage the development of a training program with greater curricular consistency and operational value compared to the current instruments in Romania, which should be experimentally validated and constitute a useful reference in the development of teachers' transversal competencies.

References

- Albulescu, I. (2024). Argumentarea unui punct de vedere personal. Albulescu, I., Catalano, H (coord). *Educația socială*. București: Didactica Publishing House.
- Albulescu, I., Catalano, H (coord) (2021). *E-Didactica. Procesul de instruire în mediul online*. București: Didactica Publishing House.
- Bunăiașu, C.M. (2015). *Direcții de dezvoltare a curriculumului intercultural în România, din perspectiva dimensiunii europene a educației*. București: Editura Muzeul Literaturii Române
- Bunăiașu, C.M. (2017). The Development of Intercultural Curriculum from the Perspective of Education for International Solidarity. Tilea, M., Duță, O.A. Reșceanu (coord.). *A. Sustainable and Solidary Education*. Peter Lang Edition.
- Bunăiașu, C.M., Strungă, A.C. (2016). Perspectives and modalities in order to develop the didactic staff's intercultural competences. *Social Sciences and Education Research Review*, 3, 2/2016, 62-70
- Bunăiașu, C.M., Vlăduțescu, Ș., Strungă, A.C. (2014). Managerial competences in the field of university curriculum for virtual learning communities. *Romanian Journal of Multidimensional Education*, 6/2014, 2,17-25.
- Dumitru, D. (2013). *Cui îi e frică de gândirea critică? Programele educaționale intergrate și gândirea critică*. București: Editura Universității din București.
- Gavreliuc, A. (2011). *Psihologie interculturală*. Iași: Editura Polirom.

- Joița, E. (2006). *Instruirea constructivistă – o alternativă*. București: Editura Aramis.
- Morin, O. (coord). (2018). *ACTECIM – Studiu de caracterizare a competențelor transversale. Erasmus + proiect*
- Strungă, A. (2014). *Imaginile mentale europene și identitatea profesională în formarea cadrelor didactice*. București: Editura Universitară
- Tilea, M., Morin, O., & Duță, O. A. (2019). *Competențe transversale în educația pentru dezvoltare durabilă și solidaritate internațională/Transversal Competences in Education for Sustainable Development and International Solidarity*. Craiova: Universitaria.
- Tilea, M., Duță, O-A., Reșceanu, A., (2021), “Extracurricular Projects in the Romanian Educational Context: Between Students’ Mere Participation and Genuine Engagement”. In *INTED2021 Proceedings, 15th International Technology, Education and Development Conference, March 8th-9th, 2021* — Valencia, Spain, 2021, IATED Academy. ISBN: 978-84-09-17939-8 / ISSN: 2340-1079. doi: 10.21125/inted.2021.
- Tilea, M., Resceanu, A., & Resceanu, I. (2021). *Mind-changing perspectives on education: A content analysis of young people’s storytelling-bases interviews*. *Analele Universității Ovidius Constanța Seria Filologie*, XXXII(2), 394–411.
- Trincherro, R. (2016). *Opérationnaliser les competences sur la citoyenneté. Matériaux de travail pour le projet ACTECIM*.

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